

On The Fractional Fundamental Boson

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Abstract

Our vision is to theoretically establish a fractional charged elementary vector boson of spin unity and also an equation to compute the mass of elementary but charged weak gauge boson analogous to charge boson here predicted.

Fabulous theoretical framework explains the particle physics laws and force along with their interactions such model which theorist call as a standard model. Four fundamental forces in which electromagnetic and weak force are previously unified [1] in complete agreement with experiments. We previously predicted a vector boson [2] of charge one-third and now if we explain all vector boson charges in one equation we simply obtain a unified relation in order of

$$\{A' - W^+ - B' - g^L - g^V - \gamma - Z^0\} = 0$$

To obey simple pattern a vector (spin unity) boson A' of charge must be of fourth- third should exist. Other bosons g^L , is the charge of gluon, g^V is the charge of graviton, γ charge of photon, B' is the new boson independently predicted by the same author see ref 2 which must possess charge $+1/3$, Z^0 charge of z boson. The mechanism that breaks the gauge symmetry in vacuum was earlier proposed [3]. Weinberg's model shows that spin 1 charged weak boson's field is given by

$$W_\mu = 2^{-\frac{1}{2}}(A_\mu^1 + iA_\mu^2)$$

The neutral z boson field would be

$$Z_\mu = (g^2 + g'^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}(gA_\mu^3 + g'B_\mu)$$

g is the $SU(2)$ gauge coupling and g' is the $U(1)$ gauge coupling

For electromagnetic boson field we have

$$A_\mu = (g^2 + g'^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}(-gA_\mu^3 + g'B_\mu)$$

Traditionally w boson mass would be

$$M_W = \frac{1}{2}\lambda g$$

λ is the vacuum expectation value of Higgs field ≈ 246 GeV

Our task requires no need of z boson mass

For photon mass

$$M_A = 0$$

We will show a mathematical relation to compute the approximate mass of w boson

$$M_W = \frac{2}{311}M_Z\alpha^{-1}$$

λ is the Higgs field vacuum expectation value=246 GeV, α is the fine structure

constant = $1/137.035999173$, M_Z is the mass of an z boson = 91.18 GeV thus simply one can find that SU(2) gauge coupling for w boson is consequently given by

$$g = \frac{4}{311\lambda} M_Z \alpha^{-1}$$

We obtain that the mass of w boson is 80.35 GeV agreeing quite well with experiments.

This predicted particle according to this theory of electric field must possess decay to certain particles (because up quarks have charge +2/3) or any two other particle of charge 2/3

$$A' \rightarrow u + u \text{ (two up quark)}$$

As in beta positive decay there is also an emission of positron so such case A' should follow

$$A' \rightarrow e^+ + d' \text{ (d' is antidown quark)}$$

The first decay of the boson to a pair of up quarks or a pair of quarks of charge +2/3 will therefore strongly establish the proposed hypothesis.

The only prediction here we draw is the prediction of spin one vector boson of possible fractional charge. Collider experiments are suggested to test our theory.

References

[1] Phys. Rev. Lett. 19, 1264 – Published 20 November 1967

[2] <http://vixra.org/pdf/1809.0328v1.pdf>

[3] Phys. Rev. Lett. 13, 508 – Published 19 October 1964